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Electoral Malpractices And Political Instability In Nigeria: A Case Study Of The 2023 General Elections

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ABSTRACT

The study assesses the effect of election rigging on political instability in the 2023 general elections using selected four local government areas across the three senatorial districts in Delta State Nigeria, namely Ethiope West, Ethiope East, Oshimili South and Warri North Local Government Areas. The objectives of the study is to evaluate the factors that contributed to the electoral malpractices in the 2023 general elections leading to political instability in the LGAs. The study which was anchored on the Harold Lasswell theory of politics utilized a sample of 400 respondents and employed seven questionnaires in line with the objective. Using Likert scale descriptive statistics, the study found that political influence, inadequate security measures, poor regulatory framework, intimidation of voters, lack of voters' education, among others were the overwhelming factors that contributed to electoral malpractice in the 2023 general elections in the local governments. Among other things, the study recommended for the need to ensure active participation of the youth demographic by addressing the underlying social and economic concerns affecting the youth thereby redirecting their energy towards positive civic engagement for national development.

Keywords: Election Rigging, Political Instability, 2023 General Elections, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electoral violence remains a significant challenge to democratic consolidation in Nigeria. Over the years, the country's transition to democratic governance has been marred by frequent violent conflicts during election periods, undermining the legitimacy of electoral outcomes and eroding public trust in democratic institutions. Notably, Nigeria has a check history of discontinuous elections, spanning over a period of eighty years, beginning from 1923 when the first election was held. The 1923 election did not allow for popular participation mainly because the 1922 Constitution in Nigeria that provided the legal framework for the election laid down highly restrictive electoral law for the country. This led to a situation where the initial elections in Nigeria were not based on universal adult suffrage but rather were guided by an income-based male suffrage. The restrictive nature of the colonial electoral system was exemplified by

the regulation which stipulated that only adult males with a gross national income, from all sources, of not less than one hundred pounds (£100.00) were allowed to vote. Under this circumstance, only a small fraction of adult males was considered eligible to vote. According to Ameh-Ogigo (2025), only 3,000 and 1,000 out of an estimated 40,000 and 10,000 adult African males in Lagos and Calabar, respectively were eligible to vote.

Good and acceptable governance depends on the formation of stable political systems and the shift towards democracy that has become a global norm. Due to apparent conviction hinged on free, fair and credible elections, participatory governance, and respect for human rights, democratization processes have received a lot of attention globally in the last few decades (Ayanleye, 2013, Adetunji *et al.*, 2024). A turning point in the political history of the African continent was the post-Cold War wave of democratization that swept through the continent. According to Ayanleye (2013), countries in Africa started the process of democratization with the intent to do away with authoritarian rule and embrace a more inclusive and representative political systems. Nevertheless, Tsuwa, *et al.*, (2020) submitted that despite these initiatives, the initial excitement around this democratic wave soon gave way to hopelessness as numerous African nations demonstrated that enthroning democracy requires more than just elections. In addition to being marred by a flawed electoral process, violations of human rights, corruption, and poor governance, many of these third-wave democracies in Africa also tended towards one-party dominance.

A number of elections were held across Africa in 2024. Available statistics revealed that twenty African nations held presidential or national elections, representing over 37% of the continent's countries. This underscores a significant engagement in the democratic process wherein leaders are chosen to govern for the ensuing electoral terms. The multitude of elections necessitates a comprehensive evaluation of Africa's overall governance quality and the extent of democratic consolidation. Of the twenty scheduled elections, 30% occurred in Southern Africa, 25% in West Africa, 20% in North Africa, and 10% in Central Africa. Most elections in Africa normally lead to unrest and violence. For instance, the general elections held in Comoros 14th January, 2024 led to unrest where many people were killed. An electoral commission declared President Azali Assoumani the winner with 62.97% of the vote cast in Comoros election. However, the Comoros Supreme Court later validated the President's win with 57.2% of the vote, sparking allegations of electoral fraud from opposition parties. Consequently, protests erupted in Moroni on January 17th and 18th, resulting in widespread property damage. Law enforcement responded with teargas and bullets, resulting in casualties and arrests, prompting the imposition of a curfew on January 18th to restore order.

A significant landmark in Nigeria's democratic history was the transition from military to civilian administration in 1999. Nonetheless, Nigeria has had a number of challenges in maintaining democratic governance which include but not limited to problems of transparent electoral system and political stability. Scholars in the academic community continue to be more than passingly interested in Nigerian elections because only legitimate elections can strengthen and maintain the nation's fledgling democracy. Nigeria has experienced increasing disappointments and anxiety over the course of the year regarding the conduct of peaceful, free, and fair elections whose outcomes are widely acknowledged and respected throughout the nation (Osumah & Aghemelo, 2011; Ekweremadu, 2011). A democratic regime cannot exist without elections and there is currently a genuine risk that holding regular, fairly competitive and transparent elections will be mistaken for democracy (Hounkpe & Gueye, 2010).

2. BRIEF REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Harold Lasswell's Theory of Politics

This theory was developed in 1902 by Harold Lasswell, an influential political scientist known for seminar studies of power relations and of personality and politics and for other major contributions to contemporary behavioral political science. He authored more than 30 books and 250 scholarly articles on diverse subjects, including international relations, psychoanalysis and legal education. A prolific writer, Lasswell viewed political science as the study of changes in the distribution of value patterns in society, and, because distribution depends on power, the focal point of his analysis was power dynamics. He

defined values as desired goals and power as the ability to participate in decisions, and he conceived political power as the ability to produce intended effects on other people. In *Politics: Who Gets What, When, how* (1963),—a work whose title later served as the standard lay definition of politics—he viewed the elite as the primary holders of power, but in *Power and Society: A Framework for Political Inquiry* (1950), written with Abraham Kaplan, the discussion was broadened to include a general framework for political inquiry that examined key analytical categories such as person, personality, group, and cultural prolific writer.

Lasswell moved toward a moralistic posture, calling for the social and biological sciences to reorient themselves toward a science of social policy that would serve the democratic will for justice. Other features of political science that can be traced to Lasswell include system theory, functional and role analysis, and content analysis. In Lasswell's view of power, he argued that in political science and sociology, the capacity to influence, lead, dominate, or otherwise have an impact on the life and actions of others in society. The concept of power encompasses, but is not limited to, the notion of authority. Unlike authority, which implies legitimacy, power can be exercised illegitimately.

Frustration-Aggression Theory

The theory was developed by Dollard *et al.*, (1939) who postulated that aggressive behavior normally follow frustration. According to this view, violent behavior stems from a person's inability to pursue their goals because of external factors that prevent them from doing so. An aggressive person may shift their animosity onto a helpless bystander when they are unable to address the aggressor directly. Relative deprivation is an alternate explanation to this one that proposes a discrepancy between desired and achievable outcomes. Angry outbursts and violent actions are more probable the wider the gap. Some people have argued that the frustration-aggression approach is flawed because it focuses too much on the victim's inner workings. According to Lupsha (1971), political violence is intricate and interrelated, involving the concept of deprivation and the subsequent action or reaction to that deprivation. He argues that angry outbursts do not necessarily lead to physical violence, that people can feel upset without resorting to violence, and that violent acts can happen in any community. A lot of people have problems with the frustration-aggression paradigm, yet it helps a lot when trying to figure out why people get violent during elections. When considering that aggressive or frustrated behavior might lead to violent acts, the theory's value becomes clear. People are more likely to respond violently in order to defend themselves when they are pushed beyond their limits by excessive pressure.

Concept of Election

Election has been defined in various dimensions. Ighodalo (2022) averred that election is one of the major instruments for selecting political officeholders. He argued that election serves as means of ensuring accountability and mobilization of the citizenry for political participation but noted that elections in Nigeria have always been characterized by malpractices which include election rigging, snatching and stuffing of ballot boxes, political intimidation and assassination prior to, during and after elections. The result is that unpopular governments are brought to power with the leading to legitimacy crisis, breakdown of law and order and general threat to security. He posited that adaptation of liberal democratic system that will suit the country's cultural values and peculiarities should be applied to lay the basis for people centered development strategies thereby empowering them to be active participants in policy making and implementation, under a political climate characterized by the rule of law and constitutionalism. Unless these categorical steps are taken, the author submitted that the country may experience another democratic breakdown that will spell doom for the nation-state.

According to Sogbaïke and Akporhonor, (2021), election is the process by which citizens of nation state decide their rulers and assign persons to leadership positions which entails voluntary participation in the choice of leadership positions. The success and performance of elections indicate how peaceful and effective democratic transitional processes are, and reflect the level of political development and systemic stability. For effective change of leadership by choice to hold, there is the need for the formation of political system which is the process of interest aggregation. To achieve this political parties serve as the main focus as they are structured and designed to gain or hold the major policy making positions in a system and to recruit political leaders among others.

Elections constitute an essential principle in liberal democracy. Election in a democracy is very important because it is through which that the expression of the people are shown via legitimacy and leadership succession. According to Dickerson, et al (1990) election is defined as a post mortem that investigate the record of office holders whose actual performance may have little to do with promises made when they were previously elected. This is a way of censuring, reposing function in a ruler that is popularly accepted and ejecting an unpopular leader. This method shuns mutiny and chaos in a system hence it reflects peaceful hand-over from one administration to the other so long as the process is devoid of election rigging. In a democracy, election is a fundamental ingredient and a utmost test of political participation it is defined as a process of selecting officers and representatives of an organization by votes of its qualified members. The process gives the citizens the right to vote at regular intervals among competing leaders and policies (Bedlolman 1993). Also, election has been defined as a process in which electorates chose government officials using a voting system. This is the mechanism by which a democracy fills elective offices in the legislature, and perhaps the executive and judiciary. The most common election methods or electoral systems can be categorized as either proportional or majoritarian. Among the former are party-list proportional representation and additional member system. Among the latter are first past the post (relative majority), and absolute majority many countries have growing electoral reform movements, which advocate systems such as approval voting, single transferable vote, instant runoff voting or a Condorcet method. The rules by which an elections is conducted (especially the voting system used) can have wide ranging effects on the character and outcome of the election.

Nigeria has organized thirteenth general elections and numerous regional, state, and local government elections between 1954 and 2023. Of these elections, the 1965, 1983 and 2011 witnessed significant incidents of post-election violence. All the general elections organized in Nigeria since 1954 can be broadly categorized into two: consolidation and transition elections. Transition elections are the general elections organized by a departing political authority, which include those organized by the departing colonial authorities in 1954 and 1959, and those organized by military regimes in 1979, 1993 and 1999. On the other hand, consolidation elections are general elections organized by a civilian regime and are intended to consolidate civil rule. These include the 1964/65, 1983, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023 general elections (Ameh-Ogigo, 2025).

Concept of Election Fraud

Election fraud is a subversion of the constitution and democratic forms of government instituted by the constitution. It is the theft of people's mandate. The common methods of election rigging in Nigeria include dumping of ballot boxes stuffed with pre-thumb-printed ballot papers, falsification of results by increasing a candidate's votes and decreasing those of his opponents, fraudulent announcement of losing candidate and so on (Ologbenia 2003). Election rigging according to Nwabueze (2003) refers to electoral manipulations which are palpable illegalities committed with a corrupt, fraudulent or sinister motive to influence an election in favour of a candidate (s) by way such as illegal voting , bribery, treating and undue influence, intimidation and other form of force exerted on the electorates, falsification of results, fraudulent announcement of a losing candidate as the winner (without altering the recorded results). Election rigging was perfected in the elections conducted in previous years and the just concluded elections. Election rigging connotes any form of undue authority or power that influence and manipulate election result in a dubious way to protect a particular interest against the interest of the generality of the masses. When the interest of the people are articulated in a free and fair election, the government in power tend to enjoy the sovereign legitimacy of the people but election rigging can thwart the interest of the people hence the dubious imposition of an unpopular candidate. The sad end is governments' lack of people's support which is one of the basic principles of democracy.

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Concept of Political Instability

In the view of Ameh and Usman (2024), political instability states that frequent or ongoing political violence, civil unrest undermine what is essential for stable or functional governance. The point is that political instability occurs when the processes which allow for peaceful transition of power (elections) are broken, resulting in social unrest and governance collapse. Political instability weakens democratic institutions, damages economic development and reduces effectiveness of the rule of law. Within the realm of electoral violence, the concept contends that violence impairs electoral trust, and that, in turn, political actors resort to violence or coercion to achieve power. This instability of the political environment and lack of legitimacy of the elected governments fuels it. Political instability also helps make sense of violence created in countries such as Nigeria where electoral violence is common, and how this violence affects the long-term democratic development of the state.

This refers to the prevention of conflict and the promotion of peace. On the other hand, political instability encompasses absence of peace in a political governance. Generally, the concept of political stability comprehends the following scope of meanings and nuances: The absence of violence, government longevity, the existence of a legitimate constitutional regime, absence of structural change, and, a multifaceted societal attribution (Tsuwa *et al.*, 2020). More conventionally, political stability entails the absence of domestic civil conflicts and violent behavior. On the contrary, political instability refers to a situation where a political governance is engulfed with violence perpetuated mostly by miscreants, presence of unconstitutional regime, illegitimate constitutional governance and so on.

Essentially, a stable polity is seen as a peaceful law-abiding society where decision making and politico-societal change are the result of institutionalized and functional procedures and not the outcome of anomic processes which resolve issues through conflict and aggression (Hurwitz, 1973: 449). To Osaghae (1995) political stability whether in democracy or quasi democracy, could not be pursued for its own sake. In the circumstances of developing countries, what was (and still) more important is good government that responds positively to the demands and expectations of the people. He further asserts that, only a government that performs well can be stable, if what sustains it in power is voluntary support or consent of the citizens. Simply put, political stability means the prevalence of peace, political order and sustainable progress in a polity over a period of time. It is characterized by amiable civil relations and peaceful socio-political change that forecloses.

Political stability in any form of government has to involve the stable realization of political essence of that form of government. Political stability of a communal gerontocracy in villages and small towns headed by elders under an age grade system means the continuation of the exercise of power by those who have reached the appropriate age at various levels of the system. Political stability of the type of democracy provided for in our constitution means the continuation of the exercise of power by those freely elected by the people of this country for specific periods with definite mandates which conform to the fundamental objectives and directive of the principles of state policy clearly defined in chapter 11 of the constitution.

A careful and rigorous analysis of political instability in any society requires an application of useful and reliable instruments of interpretation of phenomena. Without such tools, any adventure into that exercise

will be tantamount to navigating in the high seas without a compass. Two deeper roots and permutations of political instability, albeit complementary, approaches which include (a) institutional functionalism and (b) structuralism. The former explains instability by focusing on the interface between institutionalization and political participation, while the latter gives pride of place to social stratification and the configuration of power relations among social forces within and without the ambit of the state. Political process as an economic political factor have threatened the stability of the Nigerian political system which in most cases has given rise or cause a set back to the smooth running of the transition to democratic program.

The concept of political instability varies as employed in the numerous studies. It has been understood as the propensity of a change in the executive arm of government either by constitutional or unconstitutional means (Alesina et al., 1992). In 1995, the study of Mauro however noted that Italy had more than fifty changes in government between 1945 and 1995 and the country still remained relatively stable during the period and yet Italy is one of the developed countries of the world. Could therefore, high propensity of political instability among African countries responsible for their problems of underdevelopment among others? Another dimension is to define political instability as either a change in the existing political system or a challenge to it (Mbaku, 1992). Mbaku reinforced the argument of Morrison and Stevenson (1971) which defined and widen the scope of “change in the government” and “challenges to the government”. Change in the government involved reshuffling of the cabinet, removal and subsequent replacement of the executive or head of state as well as change in political parties’ representation after successfully election in any country while challenges to the government constitute all factors that can pose treat to the current regime of government such as attempted or unsuccessful coups and other forms of plot sponsored by the opposition party against the government. Morrison and Stevenson (1971) understood political instability as a condition in political arrangements in which institutional structure of authority breakdown and the expected compliance to political authority is replaced by political violence. The study further stressed that political instability involved the understanding of differences between the power of the national elite that rule the country and that of non-elite and as a result, there are three types of political instability: elite, communal and mass political instability.

3. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study focused on the systematic analysis of election rigging and political instability as it concerned the 2023 general elections. It was found out by the study that issues of election rigging during elections remain a reoccurring decimal in Nigeria which undoubtedly affect the credibility of electoral processes in Nigeria. The main reason for undertaking the study is because of the fact that electoral irregularities during the 2023 general elections in Nigeria elucidates critical issues that demand immediate attention and concerted efforts.

Therefore, the findings of this study stress the need for comprehensive and collaborative efforts to address electoral irregularities in Nigeria. The diverse approach should involve legal reforms, institutional restructuring and societal interventions. As stakeholders come together, including the government, electoral bodies, media and civil society, the goal should be to strengthen democratic practices, uphold the integrity of the electoral system and restore public trust in the democratic process.

A major conclusion therefore is that continuous research and monitoring of electoral processes is required since election rigging is a continuous process. As such regular assessments enable the detection of emerging difficulties, allowing for appropriate modifications and improvements. Finally, collaboration among researchers, civil society organizations, and government agencies will help to create a dynamic and adaptive election system.

On the basis of the above findings, the following recommendations are proffered.

In the first place, a key observation is the active participation of the youth demographic, possibly driven by perceived irregularities. To harness this enthusiasm constructively, strategies should be devised to address the underlying social and economic concerns affecting the youth, redirecting their energy towards positive civic engagement.

Likewise, the study highlighted specific electoral irregularities such as vote-buying, ballot box snatching, harassment of voters and unauthorized result announcements. These issues demand immediate attention, with a focus on investigating and rectifying problems associated with the delegate system, including the influx of foreign currency compromising the integrity of primary elections and candidate selection. Furthermore, with regard to the media especially social media, which plays a pivotal role in shaping narratives and political discourse during elections, caution is pertinent. While recognizing its impact, regulations must be established to address the spread of misinformation, hate speech and abuse on the platforms. Emphasizing responsible reporting by traditional and social media outlets is crucial to fostering a positive information environment and preventing the exacerbation of existing societal tensions.

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